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|-------------|------------|--------------------|------------------|
| stomach | pancreas | vein | tendon |
| small bowel | lung | kidney with fascia | ligament |
| colon | heart | tube | thymus |
| liver | cartilage | ovary | trachea |
| kidney | bone | aorta | fur |
| spleen | skin | pleura | subcutaneous fat |
| bladder | muscle | blood | diaphragm |
| omentum | peritoneum | visceral fat | |

dataset I & VI:
 rat physiological
 pig physiological
 (9 organs)

dataset V:
 rat physiological
 extended
 (31 organs)

